

Intraoperative Nursing Care for COVID-19 Patients: Lived Experiences of Operating Room Nurses Amidst the Pandemic

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Citation: Elbridge T. Cubero*, Leo Francis L. Silva, N Lysette A. Lao. Intraoperative Nursing Care for COVID-19 Patients: Lived Experiences of Operating Room Nurses Amidst the Pandemic. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2025;4(3):1-16.

Received Date: 14 March, 2025; **Accepted Date:** 17 March, 2025; **Published Date:** 19 March, 2025

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought unprecedented challenges to healthcare systems worldwide, exposing healthcare workers to high stress and risk levels. Intraoperative nurses, who work in high-stress environments, have been particularly affected by the pandemic. This qualitative research aimed to explore the lived experiences of intraoperative nurses amidst the pandemic. This study employed the qualitative descriptive-phenomenological design. Seven OR nurses were purposefully chosen to participate in the in-depth face-to-face interview, while seven OR nurses participated in the focus group discussion via the Zoom platform. Utilizing Collaizzi's method of data analysis revealed that OR nurses' experiences during intraoperative care to their patients include the themes: Fighting the Unseen Enemy, Dreading Contamination, Adhering to Safety Protocol, Preparing Oneself, and Struggling with PPEs. The OR nurses' coping methods were contained in the themes: Emerging Triumphant, Teamwork makes the Dream Work, Positive Mindset, Holistic Support, and Adaptive Strategies. The themes Towards Sustainability, Opportunity for Teamwork, Addressing Structural Improvement, and Call for Manpower Maximization were the insights the OR nurses shared with their fellow nurses and the nursing practice in general. Further efforts must continue to discover how to improve safety and work conditions for OR nurses handling COVID-19 patients.

Keywords: Health Science; Intraoperative Nursing Care; Descriptive Phenomenology; Davao City

INTRODUCTION

Nurses are the front-liners in the battle against COVID-19, performing the most critical roles and responsibilities. The experiences of operating room nurses who perform lengthy surgical procedures while wearing a triple-phase suit—first a scrub suit, then hazmat with complete PPE that includes face shields, goggles, N95, boots, and a sterile surgical gown—are much more severe in comparison to the rest of the nurse population. Lee (2020) asserts that operating room nurses are most at risk of contracting the virus due to their involvement in aerosol-generating procedures (AGP) in a closed environment during intubation and extubation.

Accordingly, the American Operating Room Association stated that the COVID-19 crisis had put operating room staff under a lot of stress and pressure, and they have to deal with many care challenges, all of which have affected their ability to perform professionally. This might result from the challenging and stressful environment in the operating room.^[1]

The International Council of Nurses (ICN) reported that as of June 2020, at least 90,000 healthcare workers had contracted COVID-19 and that the epidemic has claimed the lives of more than 260 nurses.^[2] As a preventive measure, the World Health Organization (WHO) and other medical authorities have created evidence-based methods and techniques for preventing infection during the COVID-19 pandemic. WHO strictly recommends standard preventive measures for OR nurses handling patients, such as wearing WHO-recommended N95 masks, protective gowns, face shields, and complete PPE.^[3]

The Philippine News Star (2022) reported that COVID-19 infection among healthcare workers in the Philippines had reached 3,114. In Davao Region, the Manila Bulletin (2021) reported that the virus infected 1,838 healthcare personnel as of January 13th, 2021, with 233 hospitalized, 1,595 recovered, and 10 died.

O'Glasser and Schenning (2022) and Sulayao and Magnaye (2022) argue that the COVID-19 pandemic's lack of explicit guidelines caused operating room personnel to feel unsure and confused. Thobaity and Alshamarie (2020) argue that more study is needed to examine the experiences of OR nurses working on the front lines.

METHODS

Qualitative descriptive phenomenology is a research methodology designed to provide a rich and detailed description of the phenomenon under investigation, such as the intra-operative experiences of OR nurses during the COVID-19 pandemic. It allows for a flexible and adaptable data collection and analysis approach, particularly useful when studying a rapidly evolving situation.

This research was conducted at a tertiary- level government healthcare facility in Davao City, Davao Del Sur. This facility has five Operating units: the Main Operating Room, Ambulatory Surgery,

Heart Center, Orthopedics, and Cancer Institute. This study selected only Main Operating Room as the only source of participants since they were the only unit handling COVID-19 patients.

Utilizing the purposeful selective sampling technique, the researcher chose fourteen participants based on inclusion criteria that satisfy the researcher that they can best provide information on the lived experiences of intraoperative nurses caring for COVID-19 during 2020–2022. Seven participants for in-depth interviews (IDI) and seven for focus group discussions (FGD) were chosen based on inclusion criteria that the participants have at least 6 months of exposure to Main OR during the start of the pandemic from 2020 to the present and with the Benner's level of nursing experience must be proficient or expert. The primary data sources were narratives from one-on-one in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. The secondary data sources included recent studies, articles, journals, and reviews of related literature. The duration of the face- to-face interview was approximately 30 minutes.

After the interview, the recorded audio was translated, put into writing in phrases, and verified against the transcribed data. Transcription was read and reread, significant statements were extracted, meanings were formulated, cluster themes and emergent themes were aggregated, an exhaustive description was developed of

the phenomenon's essential structure or essence, a report was generated of the fundamental form of the phenomenon, and the findings of the study were validated through participant feedback.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Participant	Sex	Age	Marital Status	Number of years or months in the OR	Length of Service in SPMC	Study Group
P 1	Male	38	Single	9 years	10 years	IDI
P 2	Male	43	Married	10 years	10 years	IDI
P 3	Male	42	Married	7 years	7 years	IDI
P 4	Male	31	Single	6 years	6 years	IDI
P 5	Female	30	Single	7 years	7 years	IDI
P 6	Female	31	Single with child	8 years	8 years	IDI
P 7	Male	39	Married	8 years	8 years	IDI
P 8	Male	44	Married	8 years	8 years	FGD
P 9	Male	48	Married	10 years	10 years	FGD
P 10	Female	29	Married	4 years	4 years	FGD
P 11	Male	31	Married	9 years	9 years	FGD
P 12	Male	33	Married	8 years	3 years	FGD
P 13	Female	31	Single with child	8 years	8 years	FGD
P 14	Male	39	Married	8 years	8 years	FGD

All of the participants have had at least 6 months of exposure to COVID-19 facilities in the Main Operating Room during the pandemic period of 2021–2022, the participants are adults ranging in age from 31 to 48, and the median is 39 years old. There are 10 male and 4 female participants. Five are single, and the rest, 9, are married. All of them are assigned in the Main Operating Room. The lowest length of service in the tertiary level government hospital is 4 years, while the longest is 10 years.

Through extracting significant statements, creating formulated meanings, and developing cluster and emergent themes, the participants' narratives revealed a comprehensive explanation of their lived experiences. The following section describes the emergent themes using the participants' narratives extracted from interview data. It discusses the participant's answers to the research questions: “What are the experiences of OR nurses in giving intraoperative care to COVID-19 patients?” “How do participants cope with the challenges of their experiences?” and “What insights can the participants share with fellow nurses and the nursing practice? Referring to the transcribed significant statement, L signifies line number, and P means participant.

Emergent Theme 1: Fighting the Unseen Enemy

The first emergent theme, Fighting the Unseen Enemy, details the experiences encountered by intraoperative nurses as they provide care to COVID-19 patients. The phrase describes a situation where someone is unprepared to face a sudden, invisible, and identifiable challenge or threat. Unseen Enemy indicates the invisible virus and the OR nurses' lack of standard care protocol to handle the virus during the pandemic's beginning. The experiences of intraoperative nurses are likened to a war where fear is imminent and surviving and winning are the primary goal. This theme uncovers and explains the preparations and challenges of the participants as they fought the unseen enemy. The participant continued to fight the unseen enemy by providing intraoperative care, despite the fear of contamination, PPE scarcity, and lack of protocol because they had accepted their fate.

The experiences of intraoperative nurses in fighting the unseen enemy include Dreading Contamination, Adhering to Safety Protocol, Preparing Oneself, and Struggling with PPEs. Knowing how to effectively fight the unseen enemy is essential to protect the OR nurses and lessen the overall stress as they care for COVID-19 patients.

Cluster Theme 1.1 Dreading Contamination

The first cluster theme is Dreading of Contamination. The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant psychological impact on OR nurses as they handle COVID-19 patients in the intra-operative phase. It has caused fear, anxiety, and uncertainty. Fear of contracting the virus, uncertainty about the future, and worries about loved ones can cause extreme anxiety and fear in intraoperative nurses. This cluster was expressed by the participants through these statements:

"My main concern before we are in the COVID OR, my main fear is exposure to COVID-positive patients. So that raises a lot of worries in my mind because going to work and knowing that you are going to assist in the procedure with COVID-19 positive patients is the fear that you might get COVID as well." (L 161 to 164, P1)

"Challenges mentally, this is number one for me, the heaviest for me because after you wear the PPE even though it was checked by the PPE checker if there was no break, but what if it got caught in something and sustained a tear then I need to take a shower. If possible, I'd bathe in alcohol, I would do it." (L260 to 262,

P4)

"It's terrifying because the virus is deadly. We cannot deny the fact that there are lot of our colleagues that are front liners that have passed away." (L 1037 to 1039, P 11)

"But the most challenging for me of all would be the anxiety. Because you know that the patient is positive and he has coughed in front of you." (L 1131 to 1133, P9)

The main psychological effects of front-liners in this pandemic were fear, vulnerability, and overall psychological distress. Analyzed studies have shown that the primary psychological impact most verbalized by nurses are fear and anxiety.^[4] The unseen enemy is not just feared to be contracted by oneself, but also of the risk of spreading it to loved ones, as verbalized in these statements:

"I know that there is nothing perfect in what I wear, but I am confident that there is no damage, and I am confident with myself that whether I touch the patient, I am well protected." (L 608 to 610, P 2)

"I was exposed to a patient at work, I was diagnosed with COVID-19 positive as a result of the swabbing test that I have undergone, so I was sent to a quarantine facility, and luckily, God forbid I went home when I got diagnosed because before releasing the result I went home. It was my fault for not knowing the swab test result, so I was already at home with my mother and father when the results came. So, the fear instilled in me knowing that I was positive and exposing my parents and that condition was dreadful." (L178 to 183, P 1)

Family is one of the core support systems of everyone, and the idea of bringing the virus to them has been dreadful for the participants. As indicated in the study of Ergen in 2022, OR nurses fear the risk of contracting the disease and infecting their loved ones. This is like the study of Galehdar (2020),^[4] that OR nurses fear infecting their family members or relatives.

Cluster Theme 1.2 Adhering to Safety Protocol

The second cluster theme, Adhering to Safety Protocol, details compliance with updated infection prevention and control protocols to prevent cross-contamination. Changes to comply with safety refers to modifications or adjustment made to a system, process, or environment to ensure that it meets safety standards and regulations. This cluster was expressed by the participants through these statements:

"Then we make sure when we come in the red zone or when we cater to patients with COVID-19, we make sure that we are equipped with a mask, PPE, shoes, boots so that it is safe for us and we don't catch the illness." (L136 to 138, P 5)

"Before going into the OR, we don the scrub suit provided by the hospital and supervisor. Then after donning with the help of the donning officer, who will guide us in wearing hazmat and PPE, boots, boot cover, N95 mask, face shield, and goggles. We use soap so that our vision will not be blurred." (L 156 to 159, P 7)

"Even if you're wearing gloves and using alcohol and with all the layers of PPE and doffing, there are dedicated containers for used PPE accordingly, for hazmat, goggles, and slippers. Then we take a shower before we go out. The devised flow was able to help." (L 1080 to 1083, P 10)

The changes in the processes and the entire system to conform to the necessary adjustments that formed part of the actions taken as a safety response to the pandemic impacted the OR nurses. As evidenced by the study of Mohammadi in 2021, one of the main challenges for operating room staff was the application of the protocols and standards of care during the COVID-19 crisis. The operating room personnel are faced with new care instructions leading to tediously executing updated protocols. The risk of COVID-19 transmission via

aerosolization and droplets is a significant concern for surgical personnel. Surgical personnel are at an increased risk when performing procedures that involve the aspiration of body fluids. Therefore, effective infection prevention and control measures must be implemented.

Cluster Theme 1.3 Preparing oneself

Preparedness is an essential variable in emergencies and disasters. Since COVID-19 is a global emergency, there is no better way to equip oneself than to be always ready. The key influences on preparedness include risk perception; preparedness perceptions such as outcome expectancy; self-efficacy; collective efficacy; previous experience; perceived responsibility; responsibility for others; coping style; and resource issues. This cluster theme titled Preparations details how the participants have prepared themselves to render service to patients. This cluster was expressed by the participants thru these statements:

"The action I did to cope with physical, what I did was to train my brain and myself. It's part of the job to wear PPE to care for COVID-19 patients. We cannot avoid this since they are just around, that's the uncontrollable situation, and then I must prepare myself before going inside the OR theatre; I eat before wearing my scrub suit. We must change scrub suits, for we deeply think that is not good; you know how deadly the pandemic is. It chooses no one; when it can kill someone, it will kill." (L 543 to 547, P 4) "For mentally, you need to be prepared regarding concerns. Be cautious in the area because there are scenarios when you come in, and you are not prepared mentally, you'd easily pass out, which would affect you physically when you are not mentally prepared." (L 202 to 204, P 2)

"For me, the preparation daily for intraoperatively, you should be mentally prepared, you should be focused that even though the procedure you are only cutdown, expect the unexpected." (L 1098 to 1099, P 13)

Psychological and physical preparedness is an essential aspect of various types of preparedness.^[5] Self-efficacy and optimism were crucial factors that played a role in these frontline workers' physical and psychological preparedness. Before going to the COVID-19 OR theatre, the OR nurses conditioned their minds that the anticipated procedure would not be short but may extend for hours, so physically, they prepared themselves.

Cluster Theme 1.4 Struggling with PPEs

The third cluster, Struggling with PPEs, details the physical challenges experienced by the participants in using PPE to protect themselves and their patients. This cluster also depicts the experience participants faced in keeping themselves from contracting the virus despite the shortage of PPE. PPE is designed to protect individuals from exposure to hazardous materials or environments. However, using PPE can sometimes be challenging and uncomfortable, leading to reduced compliance and increased risk of exposure. PPE can be heavy, restrictive, and uncomfortable to wear for extended periods, causing fatigue and discomfort. Wearing masks or face shields can impair vision and make it challenging to communicate effectively with others. PPE can also cause overheating and heat stress, especially in hot and humid environments. The difficulties of the OR nurses were highly evident in these statements:

"The hardest part for me then was how hot it was when you're wearing your hazmat. Because it's so hot, your goggles and face shield would be fogging that you won't see the field. You don't know what you are passing to the surgeon, especially since there are a lot of sutures, and then you have triple gloving. And have little hands, so it's hard to hold the instruments." (L 1128 to 1131, P 9)

"So, during intraoperative, when assisting the surgeon and wearing your face shield, your visions would be impeded. In your field, it's fogging, that's why it's tough, but the interaction that you have with your patient you cannot see in your face, you rely on the voice, so it's like that use your voice and actions and taking care of your patients even though you can't see them." (L 1018 to 1022, P 9)

"Physically, wearing the hazmat is uncomfortable, and we are not used to that equipment. One more, the type of facemask, the N95, sometimes the N95 supply they provided is not fit for us, but we have to use it because it's part of the PPE that will protect us from COVID-19. The footwear, of course, is not comfortable, boots during OR number one problem, it is heavy and hard." (L 285 to 288, P 5)

Worldwide, the use of PPE is one of the primary causes of physical issues, tiredness, and stress during this period, which included sweating caused by the protective gowns, urinating and eating constraints while wearing PPE, and difficulty seeing during surgery due to their goggles fogging up. All of these could endanger the patient's life. According to,^[6] although the work of the OR nurses was the same, using additional PPE caused complications. As a result, nurses had to work more carefully under more demanding conditions. These are reflected in these accounts:

"Well, at first during the COVID-19, it was tough for all of us to wear the PPE, impedes your breathing, your vision, you're always using goggles, you'll have headaches because it's so tight. Well, given you cannot do your necessities like eating and peeing, most of us don't go out because it's very tiring to do the entire donning and doffing of PPE again. You need to go back again and change again."(L1032 to 1035, P1)

"During wearing of the hazmat, it's tiring. Aside from thinking about our patients, we are thinking double because we are thinking of our patients and our safety, especially at the start of the pandemic wherein we were really scared of acquiring the disease." (L 1047 to 1050, P13)

"You can actually control hunger, but the use of the comfort room, that would be the most difficult because you know that you're wearing your hazmat and in the critical stage of the operation, you'd be shy to ask to go out or excuse yourself during the critical stage of the operation." (L 1086 to 1088, P12)

Moreover, because of PPE scarcity highlights the difficulty the participants faced in keeping themselves from contracting the virus. The participants expressed this through these statements:

"At the start, we did not have masks. We even recycled our N95 masks because we could not get anything." (L58, P 6)

"The most tasking for our part, there are things that we know through our meetings, most of the materials that are very limited period, so we try to balance as much as possible, we maximize the people inside in terms of materials. There are materials, but they are scarce. We cannot do anything since there are limited supplies, mostly the 95. There was one time that we required everyone to reuse those." (L 1145 to 1154, P 12)

Nurses were at the forefront of the fight against COVID-19, and for this mission to be successful, they required adequate working conditions from the start. However, due to a lack of protective equipment, their working conditions were hazardous, and COVID-19 could have been contracted at any time. COVID-19 is transmitted through respiratory droplets. Individuals become infected by touching contaminated surfaces and then touching their face, specifically their mouth, eyes, or nose. COVID-19 is the most contagious disease, according to scientific evidence. There is also the possibility of infection spreading before an individual exhibit symptom. Thus, it is essential to have an adequate PPE supply in the workplace.^[7]

Emergent Theme 2: Emerging Triumphant

The second emergent theme, Emerging Triumphant, means coming out on top or victorious after facing a challenge or competition. It implies that someone or something has overcome obstacles and succeeded in a difficult situation. This emergent theme discusses the adaptations and coping mechanisms the participants used to sustain their resilience despite the ongoing pandemic. Stress is an inseparable element of nurses' work. It is also the cause of well-being disorders and the source of various diseases. Nurses' well-being and health directly impact the quality of care and patient health outcomes. An appropriate stress-coping strategy can reduce the impact of stress and mitigate its negative consequences. The COVID-19 pandemic, especially in its initial period, was a source of additional stress for nurses (Kowalczyk, 2022).

Cluster Theme 2.1 Teamwork Makes the Dream Work

This fifth cluster theme, Teamwork makes the Dream Work, describes how the participants' positive experiences reinforced positive team dynamics. A high-intensity, fast-paced environment, healthcare workers who change every shift, and rapidly evolving patient care needs make it difficult for teams to form effectively and then for these teams to work together effectively and deliver high-quality patient care. This cluster was expressed by the participants through these statements:

"I appreciated the time when I was with them (colleagues) during the pandemic because it was then when I had known them much deeper than usual when we did not have bonding. The bonding is different before and during the pandemic because of the teamwork with the doctors. There is teamwork, and there is support. We help each other always to lessen the exposure, to make the time faster with the patient." (L 408 60 412, P 5)

"About assistance inside the operating room, it is the support system working hand in hand so that tasks are easier, specifically outside and inside circulating, that he would not be hustled, communicate with outside circulating about what is lacking in the OR. You need support from colleagues, teamwork, and communication." (L 662 to 668, P 2)

"I think teamwork. Because, in times of teamwork, we did not think of ourselves so that no patient I just left behind. We help each other to finish the case." (L 1359 to 1396, P 8)

Teamwork has a significant impact as one of the adaptive strategies of the OR nurses during the onset of the pandemic. Additional demands that impacted the ability of teams to work together were introduced during COVID-19 and with the associated restructuring of care teams and care settings that occurred as a result. Since it is likely that other stressors will continue to impact healthcare systems (e.g., pandemic or otherwise), understanding what healthcare systems, hospitals, administrators, and clinicians can do to enhance opportunities for ICU teams to work together effectively in rapidly changing environments is imperative.^[8] Nursing is an outstanding profession for strengthening collaborative interprofessional practice and teamwork through communication with the other components of the health team, promoting harmony, quality in decision-making, and impacting patients directly with quality care.^[9]

Cluster Theme 2.2 Positive Mindset

The sixth cluster theme is Positive Mindset. This refers to a mental and emotional state focusing on positive outcomes, opportunities, and possibilities rather than dwelling on negative thoughts or outcomes. It involves

adopting an optimistic and proactive attitude toward life, even facing challenges or setbacks. A positive mindset can help individuals to cope with stress, build resilience, and improve overall well-being. This cluster was expressed by the participants through these statements:

"But you will not feel all of this when you're assisting inside, but you'll enjoy yourself because you have your colleagues at the same time thinking you're doing this to our patients despite the three layers of protective gear you are wearing. At the same time, it's a learning experience for us. Good job to all of us." (L 1026 to 1031, P 10)

"The reason I am still here in the OR aside from taking care of the patient is it's better for me every day is the new challenges that give me the energy regarding various cases. It's a different experience in the OR and the joy of working hand in hand with the doctors. Even if we've just assisted with the doctors, it's still awesome because it is experience." (L 462, 463, 472 to 474, P 4)

"I am happy... despite the pandemic because I dream of being an OR nurse. This is what I like, and though being an OR nurse is tiring, it is fulfilling. For me, you'll be able to help the patient from having a severe illness, then you will see after the operation that the patient would be ok, and you will hear them say thank you to you. No amount of money can be equal when a patient thanks you for your help. It's fulfilling for me, so I stayed as an OR nurse." (L 476 to 480, P 5)

A positive mindset was one of the drivers of resilience for the participants. They have shown a willingness to learn and grow from experience and to see this crisis as an opportunity for growth. Coping with traumatic events develops positive psychological experiences. During the COVID-19 pandemic, psychological resilience and effective coping strategies promoted positive psychological health outcomes among healthcare workers.^[10]

Positive thinking and optimism can help nurses improve their function and reduce job stress. This technique influences people's behavior in dealing with and overcoming stressful situations. A positive person views stressful situations with optimism and has a high opinion of his or her ability to deal with life's ups and downs. Increasing one's optimism in life increases the productivity of one's opinions and shifts one's positive thoughts, intellectual properties, and behaviors in a positive direction. Positive thinking encourages people to be persistent, pursue their goals effectively, and take steps to improve the quality of their lives.^[6]

Cluster Theme 2.3 Holistic Support

This seventh-cluster theme, Holistic Support, refers to the total support the participants received. It includes management support, social support, and seeking support from Supreme Being.

First, it highlights the importance of administrative support for frontline workers. The Managers, acting as representatives for the organization, play a significant role in staff resilience. The COVID-19 pandemic put intense pressure on healthcare workers' ability to process information, make assessments and decisions, hide their emotional reactions, contain feeling from others, and deal with ethical dilemmas. To handle all these cognitive and emotional demands, the healthcare workers needed a physically present manager who understood, supported, and cared for them. This cluster was expressed by the participants through these statements:

"I guess it's very effective because they immediately provided a hazmat which fits my size. Regarding my breathing patterns, it is still hard, so I still need to adjust. I bear with it. As to our experiences, we have no

choice. We bear with whatever PPE is available in the institution. (L 612 to 615, P 3)

"They were very approachable. As to what our concerns were, they gave it to us. For example, mineral water before needs to pay, but when the pandemic came, it was for the free refrigerator was provided, comfortable rooms to be used for taking a bath, and they were good at handling our colleagues." (L 354 to 357, P 2)

"For the supervisors, handling of people and giving emotional support." (L 1344 to 1345, P 11)

Staff appreciate the organization's support and managers' presence in times of crisis. In a study by Svantesson (2022), staff needs a physically present and responsive manager who provides support based on the needs of the workers. The workers understand their manager's difficult work situation and lack of resources, but they appreciate information dissemination and top management's participation in organizing the work. The presence of a manager creates stability and involvement among healthcare workers in a time of uncertainty and disorganization.

Moreover, another kind of support mentioned was the participants' emotional and psychological activities, which provided a sense of connection and comfort. Social support refers to the help and assistance the participants receive from their social networks, such as friends, family members, and co-workers. This cluster was expressed by the participants through these statements:

"Psychologically and emotionally, I talked with my friends and coworkers who were having difficulties at that time because, as I have said, many of us are under pressure and worry about contracting covid19 and exposing other people to the condition. So, whenever I had time, I talked to my friends and shared with them any emotional and psychological issues that I was having during that time because it helps when you talk to someone and share problems, and sometimes it is you would be responsible, and it is you would actually look for a solution to the problem. But venting your problem or talking to other people about your issue helps alleviate your sadness." (L495 to 502, P 1)

"When the pandemic was at its peak, your OR colleagues were the only people you may share your problem with because you are far from your family. They supported me. When we shared, we opened up about our worries like those with me in the apartment. We asked each other how their day was." (L 716 to 719, P 5)

"Emotionally, I make new friends with colleagues I was not close to. Like Sir Kobe, we were not 100% close before. To ease our worries emotionally, we open up with each other. We share our experiences inside. It's one way of voicing our feelings so we can adapt. That's it." (L 596 to 598, P5)

Strong social support is one of the most effective coping mechanisms for nurses. Social support, which can come from a spouse, relatives, friends, coworkers, or the community, is one of the most effective ways for people to cope with stressful events (Zhang, 2021). Nurses should be supported at all times to be happy at work. Nurses' stress responses can be significantly reduced with the help of social support (Sehularo, 2021).

Cluster Theme 2.4 Adaptive Strategies

This eight-cluster theme, Adaptive Strategies, details the techniques used by the participants in adapting their lifestyles and developing new coping strategies during the pandemic. Adaptive strategies may involve watching movies, playing games, having fun with colleagues, attending group therapy sessions, and seeking support from the supreme being. This cluster was expressed through these statements:

"Emotionally, in the working environment, I overcame it a little bit because of the help of E-sports that we

entertain before so as divert our anxiety." (SS 47, Lines 321 to 322, IP 7)

"I would complete whatever is necessary, or I try my best so that everything is complete so that they'd have that energy to work because they know that the equipment or new and as much as possible the hospital has provided. Hopefully, I can give; I would just put them into group therapy for their emotional and mental state to be normal." (L 970 to 9710, P 4)

"Since we have time to rest, I use it for Netflix and Mobile Legend to enjoy our tough moments. It's a big help that these could give us joy, but even though it's a tough time, we can address the longingness for our family." (L 1286 to 1288, P 10)

Furthermore, participants sought support from supreme beings. It shows how some participants used this adaptive technique to continue their daily struggles during the pandemic. In nursing, the relationship between spirituality and healthcare has been considered one of the pillars of modern nursing. According to Florence Nightingale, spirituality is considered an intrinsic component of human nature and 'the most profound resource and powerful healing power available to the person.' This cluster was expressed by the participants through these statements:

"My first preparation, all I can say is spiritually I pray to God for safety during caring to the patient, especially when there were still no administered vaccines to us." (L 148 to 150, P 7)

"Psychologically, during COVID-19, because there was anxiety, there was fear of the unknown, but luckily, I have faith in the Lord that I pray that he will give strength in dealing with COVID-19 so that I can help despite the difficulty in wearing PPE." (L 564 to 566, P 7)

"Unlike others, we were separated from our family during the peak of the pandemic; we were given an opportunity by God's grace." (L1295 to 1296, P 13)

Innate for us Filipinos to be devout to the religion we belong to. Faith has been one of the significant factors in our resilience, which is evident in the participants' responses. Similarly, previous studies have shown that including spiritual care in nursing benefits patients and nurses, results in greater satisfaction.^[11] In calamity and other unexpected and terrifying situations, people usually turn to religious rituals to find peace and quiet. The COVID-19 outbreak was unexpected; no one knew when the pandemic would end or if it could be avoided or treated. Nurses were more affected than others because they were more exposed to death and relied on religious rituals. Some nurses claimed they relied on religious and spiritual activities to lift their spirits and calm themselves, such as performing daily prayers. They attempted to find peace by praying to God (Irandoost, 2022).

Thus, individuals exhibit the necessary adaptations to cope with ongoing stress. Allowing oneself to have fun or express feelings through a group therapy session and communicating with the supreme being eased the burdens of the ongoing struggle. In challenging situations, having sound psychological reasoning and adaptation to hard places could help nurses better care for patients and lessen their psychological and social harm (Irandoost, 2022).

Emergent Theme 3. Towards Sustainability

This third emergent theme, Towards Sustainability is the ability to meet the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. It involves balancing economic, social, and environmental factors to ensure that resources are used equitably, responsibly, and efficiently.

Towards Sustainability is an emergent theme that features the improvements highlighted to address holistic needs for efficient execution of intraoperative services.

Cluster Theme 3.1 Need for Protocol Enhancement

This ninth cluster theme, Need for Protocol Enhancement, details improving protocols to conform with infection prevention, control, and other safety measures. This cluster details the concerns raised by the participants on their suggestions to enhance the existing process:

"When you get in the OR, we should minimize who is coming in the OR theater; the inside circulating nurse should not go out. Whatever your role is, when you are the outside circulating, you are not supposed to come in." (L 788 to 791, P 2)

"It should coincide with other departments, especially for the ward, even ICU, because our current setup we have different protocols, and the protocols of ward ER are also different, other departments do not coincide, which would make it difficult, or there is no proper communication when it comes to protocols." (L 813 to 817, P 3)

"In my observation at that time, we (colleagues) follow protocols, but there are times that others would still go on duty even if they're having cough." (L 1197 to 1198, P 9)

At times the best person who can contribute to the enhancement of an existing process is by way of the end-users, who are well-versed in the dos and don'ts. New and unique infectious disease outbreaks are a danger to healthcare providers and other leading providers because of limited awareness of the emerging threats and reliance on IPC measures that do not account for all the dynamics of the new pathogens. Theoretically, infection prevention and control prevent or stop the spread of infections in healthcare settings, making it pivotal to reducing the spread of the pandemic.^[12]

Cluster Theme 3.2 Opportunity for Teamwork

This tenth cluster theme, Opportunity for Teamwork, includes the narratives detailing missed occasions of having the participants part of the team. One of the critical characteristics of a positive team environment promotes psychological safety. To actively participate in patient care decision-making, staff must perceive that their work setting accepts and encourages collaboration and feedback. This cluster was expressed through these statements:

"Even if we give suggestions on things that we might implement, they will not listen. They only implement what is favorable to them, not addressing the issues experienced by the staff" (L 634 to 636, P 3)

"Sometimes they decide on their own; there is a problem among the Supervisors." (L741, P 6)

"If I were the head nurse, I would do more communication, I'll talk with my staff one by one if I have time, and then I'll come in the intraoperative area to observe so that at least I'd feel what the staff would feel if they are wearing the hazmat. I want to know what is lacking or what needs to be improved or talk with the nursing staff about their concerns in the intraoperative phase." (L 958 to 959, P 2)

Communication and feedback are essential for improving processes and looking into the welfare of team members. There was a failure to include staff in the discussion on those occasions, yet they are critical players in the process. Psychological safety refers to the shared belief that a work setting is a safe place to take interpersonal risks, such as speaking up, asking questions, and sharing ideas and opinions. The ongoing global

response to COVID-19 emphasizes the importance of psychological safety in healthcare teams; the continuous adaptation and redesign of services have required enhanced collaboration, engagement, creativity, innovation, and knowledge sharing across teams and organizations.^[13] Feedback is vital in improving the provision of services, as staff are internal stakeholders of the organization.

Cluster Theme 3.3 Addressing Structural Improvement

This eleventh cluster theme, Addressing Structural Improvement, details the structural needs of the OR. COVID-19 poses significant social and health risks because even asymptomatic individuals can transmit the disease. Engineering and traffic control using barriers and zones of risk are infection control strategies to reduce the contamination rate. Structural outcomes cover infrastructure and logistic needs such as equipment and materials. This cluster was expressed by the participants through these statements:

"The OR tables need to be fixed. The OR Trendelenburg side rails are not usable. At least it would be easier to operate, especially when there's positioning needed during the OR. There was a time a patient needed to do lateral. We are using hazmat and need to put the patient in lateral, but there is no positioner." (L 788 to 791, P 2)

"Regarding the physical setup in the OR, all the patients and health care workers are affected. The process flow of the OR is affected because we have different setups or different physical setups. We have the same entrance of positive and non-positive." (L 925 to 927, P 3)

"The problem that we encountered that hindered us to provide service is structural; that was our problem." (L 1363 to 1364, P 9)

The Association of Perioperative Registered Nurses (AORN) recommends that all perioperative team members promote patient safety and use evidence-based patient positioning guidelines while engaging in positioning activities. After placing patients, perioperative staff should constantly evaluate patients for compromise or damage and take remedial action to address practice violations.^[14]

There are a lot of existing structural problems in the OR that needs to be addressed by the management. Basic OR needs to provide safe and quality care, such as OR tables with functional positioners needs to be looked into, as well as addressing the need for unilateral flow of clean to dirty to prevent cross contamination whether by patients, staff, materials, or equipment. There is also a need to address staff comfort by providing air conditioning units.

Cluster Theme 3.4 Call for Manpower Maximization

The twelfth cluster theme, Call for Manpower Maximization, details analyzing the workforce and developing strategies to ensure that the right amount of people achieves the organization's objectives with the proper training and support. Adequate provision of health services is seriously affected by human resources. The main concerns in this area include inappropriate numbers, type, distribution method, and the performance of the personnel in the health sectors. In this regard, the optimal management of health human resources is considered the significant responsibility of the managers containing those activities for improving the level of competency and knowledge increase as well as developing the personnel's skills. This cluster was expressed by the participants through these statements:

"I think more training. Because there are new practices in other countries, especially in the US, that we should adapt. Even though we are senior nurses, we can already render effective care and competent care to patients

inside the OR. I think there is room for improvement for nurses in the OR to be informed, to gather knowledge with the new practices adopted by other countries so that we could implement it here in our hospital." (L 947 to 951, P1)

"When it comes to staffing, they need to improve everyone since an increasing number of nurses are resigning and working abroad. Every month there are 3-4 nurses who resign to work abroad. Until now, from last year, only a few were added to the team. A decrease in OR staffing means an increased workload for the staff. Once the workload would increase, stress levels of staff would increase." (L 823 to 827, P 3)

"In terms of staffing, we lack manpower. If additional manpower was available immediately, I think the services would have been improved." (L1385 to1386, P 8)

The nursing shortage is actually a global problem, and this was experienced by the participants, especially when the demand became high during the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. Although healthcare systems all over the world increasingly face the challenges of shortages in human resources and the inappropriate distribution of their skills, applying optimal management along with applied plans for quality improvement of these recourses can lead to improving the competencies as well as increasing the quality of services and decreasing the related challenges.^[15-23]

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This qualitative research on the lived experiences of OR nurses amidst the COVID-19 pandemic suggests improving support for OR nurses. This research can help nurse managers and healthcare leaders understand OR nurses' unique challenges, such as adequate PPE, infrastructure requirements, and how they manage to adjust and overcome the difficulties. OR nurses are in the best position to provide first-hand experience suggestions on how to comply with protocols while addressing the needs of patients.

This research can help enhance the nursing curriculum by providing valuable insights from the experiences of OR staff during the COVID-19 pandemic and any similar pandemics in the near future. It can also be used to design nursing research studies that are more relevant and meaningful to healthcare professionals.

Research conclusions from a qualitative, phenomenologically oriented study are rarely generalizable or transferrable to other contexts. The sample size was limited to 14 participants, 4 females and 10 males. Future studies should look for participants from diverse demographic backgrounds, including those with less than a year of tenure, or consider expanding to increase the number of participants from different tertiary hospitals. Future studies may focus on issues such as updated evidence- based OR protocols in handling COVID-19 and occupational satisfaction and dissatisfaction of OR nurses during the pandemic.

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